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Evaluating the Output-Oriented Technical Efficiency of Container Ports in Türkiye

Türkiye’de Konteyner Limanlarının Çıktı Odaklı Teknik Etkinliğinin Değerlendirilmesi

Araştırma Makalesi/Research Article

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Özet

Limanlar ve terminaller, dünya denizciliğinin ve küresel tedarik zincirlerinin tartışmasız biçimde kritik öneme sahip unsurlarıdır. Bu unsurlar uluslararası ticaretin kolaylaştırıcısı olmakla birlikte, aynı zamanda kritik bir darboğaz konumundadır. Limanların düşük etkinlikle çalışması, ana hat gemilerinin sefer programlarının gecikmesine ve demirleme alanlarındaki gemilerin sayısının artmasına yol açmaktadır. Bu doğrultuda, limanların düşük operasyonel etkinliği, uluslararası tedarik zincirlerinin kesintisiz işlemesi önünde önemli bir engel oluşturmaktadır. Ek olarak, düşük etkinlik yakın coğrafi bölge içerisinde faaliyet gösteren limanların rekabetçi avantajlarını koruyamamalarına da neden olmaktadır. Düşük operasyonel etkinliğin başlıca nedenleri arasında liman ekipmanı ve teknoloji yetersizliği, rıhtım ve saha kapasitesi ile ilgili sorunlar, deneyimli operatör eksikliği sayılabilir. Konunun öneminden hareketle, bu çalışmada güncel veriler ışığında Türkiye’de faaliyet gösteren ve konteyner elleçlemesi yapan 17 konteyner limanının çıktı odaklı toplam teknik verimliliği Veri Zarflama Analizi (VZA) yöntemi kullanılarak değerlendirilmektedir. Araştırmanın temel bulguları, Asya Port, DP World Yarımca, SOCAR ve Assan Port limanlarının yüksek etkinlik seviyesinde çalıştığını göstermektedir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Deniz Taşımacılığı, Liman Etkinliği, Liman Performansı, Veri Zarflama Analizi

Abstract

Ports and terminals are indisputably critical components of global shipping and global supply chains. These components not only facilitate international trade but also constitute a critical bottleneck. Low operational efficiency in ports leads to delays in mainline vessels’ service schedules and an increase in the number of vessels waiting at anchorage areas. In this regard, low operational efficiency in ports represents a significant barrier to the uninterrupted functioning of international supply chains. Additionally, low efficiency prevents ports operating within the same geographical region from maintaining their competitive advantage. The main causes of low operational efficiency may include insufficient port equipment and technology, issues related to berth and yard capacity, and a shortage of experienced operators. In light of the importance of this issue and based on recent data, this study evaluates the output-oriented overall technical efficiency of 17 container-handling ports in Türkiye,

employing the Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) method. The main findings of the research indicate that Asyaport, DP World Yarımcı, SOCAR, and Assan Port operate at high efficiency levels.

Keywords: Maritime Transport, Port Efficiency, Port Performance, Data Envelopment Analysis

1. Introduction

More than 80% of the volume of globally traded goods is transported by sea (United Nations Conference on Trade and Development, 2024). Furthermore, it is reported that the global seaborne trade is approximately 11 billion tons per year (International Chamber of Shipping, 2025). These goods are ultimately handled, stored, and transferred in ports that serve as key interfaces between the maritime and the land transportation (Notteboom et al., 2025), making ports indispensable actors in global supply chains. Yet, ports are described not only as facilitators of global trade (Yorulmaz & Baykan, 2024) but also as bottlenecks within supply chains; port congestion arising from port inefficiency can result in significant economic, commercial, and social impacts. Port congestion is primarily associated with liner vessels failing to arrive on schedule; one underlying cause is the efficiency of port operations (Qu et al., 2024).

Port efficiency is important not only for the uninterrupted and smooth functioning of global supply chains, but also for maintaining the competitive advantages of ports operating in the same region. Ports located in the same port region already compete to attract liner operators. In addition, the hinterlands of these geographically proximate ports often overlap (Ye et al., 2025), which means that the ports are also in competition on the land-side logistics interface.

Within this competitive environment, it is vital for ports to maintain technical efficiency. Building on Farrell (1957), technical efficiency in this study describes how effectively a port converts a given set of resources into the highest attainable level of output. In literature, there is a substantial number of studies on port technical efficiency, and these studies largely make use of the Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) method (e.g., Ghiara & Tei, 2021; Munim, 2020). Furthermore, in studies applying DEA, the analysis of port technical efficiency relies on commonly used input and output variables. These inputs typically include factors such as the quantity of port cranes, berth length, and the size of the terminal, whereas annual cargo throughput is commonly used as the output (e.g., De Oliveira & Cariou, 2015; Munim, 2020).

To contribute to scholarly literature and industry, it is essential to repeat port technical efficiency assessments based on annual port statistics. In this regard, the aim of the present research is to analyze the current technical efficiency of ports in Türkiye that provide container

handling services. Adopting a constant return to scale assumption, the study utilizes an output-oriented Charnes–Cooper–Rhodes (CCR) approach (Charnes et al., 1978). The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: Section 2 provides the background of research. Section 3 presents the methodological framework of the study. Section 4 reports empirical findings. Section 5 is dedicated to discussion and conclusion sections.

2. Research Background

Port efficiency and effectiveness are among the important dimensions of port performance. In particular, the issue of port efficiency is frequently addressed in the literature (e.g., Cullinane & Wang, 2010; De Oliveira & Cariou, 2015; Jiang et al., 2012). Port efficiency is predominantly approached from the standpoint of port managers, and only a limited number of studies take into account the views of port users and customers regarding port efficiency (Zhang et al., 2024). Yen et al. (2023) initially measured port performance using the DEA method, and in the subsequent stage, they examined the relationship between the DEA efficiency scores and the smart port design criteria they had weighed using the AHP method.

In literature, port efficiency is approached from different perspectives such as allocative, technical, and environmental efficiency (Zhang et al., 2024). In one instance, Kong & Liu (2021) address port city sustainability by considering port efficiency within a sustainable development perspective. The authors propose a new evaluation index to measure port city sustainability through its internal and external dimensions. In a similar effort, Chen & Lam (2018) had previously studied the sustainability efficiency of port cities by integrating port operational efficiency and city-level environmental and economic performance with a two-step DEA model. Huang et al. (2020) apply a three-step DEA solution to measure the efficiency of Shanghai and Busan Ports. The authors investigated the link between port efficiency and NOx emissions, and they found Shanghai Port is relatively inefficient compared to Busan Port.

Port technical efficiency, in turn, has traditionally focused on the association between inputs such as port equipment and infrastructure, and outputs such as TEU throughput (Sun et al., 2022). Wang et al. (2022) apply a two-step DEA procedure to measure port efficiency in Vietnam. The authors consider ship calls, terminal length, and handling equipment as input variables and cargo throughput and TEUs as output variables. In another instance, Li et al. (2022) evaluate the efficiency of 32 container terminal operators in China, considering the number and total length of berths, handling equipment and workforce size as model inputs, and they treat TEUs and net cargo weight as outputs in their DEA-based study. Martínez-Moya et al. (2024) follow a DEA metafrontier methodology to investigate time efficiency in container

port operations. The results show that dedicated transshipment hub ports are more efficient compared to gateway/mixed ports.

The current research focused on technical port efficiency. The literature review shows that the input and output variables presented in Table 1 are frequently used as the basic set of variables in technical port efficiency analyses. Therefore, to employ a simple model that does not require additional variable categories, this research adopts berth length, the number of cranes (STS and MHC), and annual container throughput in TEUs as the set of input/output variables.

Table 1. Model variables, units, and sources

Variable	Unit	Type of variable	Source
Berth Length	m	Input	Kong & Liu (2021); Chen & Lam (2018); Munim (2020)
The number of port cranes	Count	Input	Kong & Liu (2021); Chen & Lam (2018); Munim (2020)
Container throughput	TEU	Output	Kong & Liu (2021); Chen & Lam (2018); Munim (2020)

3. Methodology

DEA, proposed by Charnes et al. (1978), is a non-parametric method that is widely utilized in port efficiency analysis (Krmac & Mansouri Kaleibar, 2023; Nguyen et al., 2016; Yen et al., 2023). Therefore, the current research employs an output-oriented CCR model with constant returns to scale (Charnes et al., 1978), as shown in Eq. (1) (Ragsdale, 2007). Here, the efficiency score for port i is computed by dividing the weighted sum of that port's outputs by the weighted sum of its inputs. Moreover, in this study, a limited number of ports is analyzed, and the linear programming (LP) solution is obtained using Excel Solver. The formulation is adopted from Ragsdale (2007) while the objective function of the model is based on output maximization (annual TEU throughput) and is shown in Eq. (2). The model constraints are shown in Eqs. (3) and (4). Here, O_{ij} is the j -th output value of port i , and I_{ij} is the j -th input value of port i . Briefly, i symbolizes each port (decision-making unit), whereas j symbolizes the variable index used for the inputs and outputs. Furthermore, w_j and v_j denote the weight coefficients associated with output j and input j , respectively ($w_j \geq 0$, $v_j \geq 0$). Finally, n_o and n_l indicate how many distinct output and input measures are included in the model.

$\text{Efficiency of port "i"} = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^{n_o} O_{ij}w_j}{\sum_{j=1}^{n_I} I_{ij}v_j}$	(1)
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$\text{MAX: } \sum_{j=1}^{n_o} O_{ij}w_j$	(2)
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$\sum_{j=1}^{n_o} O_{kj}w_j \leq \sum_{j=1}^{n_I} I_{kj}v_j, \quad \forall k = 1, \dots, 17$	(3)
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$\sum_{j=1}^{n_I} I_{ij}v_j = 1$	(4)
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3.1. Data

A total of 17 ports that provide container handling services in Türkiye were selected for the DEA analysis (Table 2). Due to data-related issues, the ports of Yılport Gebze, Yılport Gemlik, Gemport, and Samsunport were not included in the study. The primary dataset was obtained from the “Turkish Port Sector 2024 Report,” and, where necessary, some data were updated with information taken from the ports’ own websites (Assan Port, 2025; Belde Port, 2025; Borusan Port, 2025; Ege Gübre Port, 2025; Limak Port, 2025; TÜRKLİM, 2024). In the employed CCR approach, the water-depth-related input was not considered as a model element, since it caused the weights of the variables “number of STS” and “number of MHC/FCC” to be calculated as 0. Therefore, the current study adopts three inputs and one output for the DEA analysis, as shown in Table 2. Definitions of the output and input metrics are provided below:

- Output: annual TEU for each port in 2023.
- Input 1: berth length (m)
- Input 2: number of the ship to shore (STS) cranes
- Input 3: number of mobile harbour cranes (MHC) and fixed cargo cranes (FCC)

Table 2. Port-level inputs and output used in the DEA model.

Port	Output 1	Input 1	Input 3	Input 4
Nr.	TEU	Berth Length (m.)	STS (qty)	MHC/FCC (qty)
1	1949882	3370	12	6
2	1719426	2010	11	4
3	1472811	2026	10	5
4	1275200	2238	9	5
5	613040	922	8	0
6	600377	1286	4	5
7	589267	1689	5	5
8	564661	784	4	5
9	441873	1115	3	9
10	432000	700	3	0
11	405479	920	4	2
12	255334	682	0	5
13	136095	1200	0	5
14	128442	450	0	4
15	96808	635	3	8
16	84523	1178	0	4
17	10939	930	0	3

Source: Assan Port (2025); Belde Port, (2025); Borusan Port, (2025); Ege Gübre Port (2025); Limak Port, (2025); TÜRKLİM (2024)

4. Findings

According to the results of the output-oriented DEA, the ports of Asya Port (2), DP World Yarımcı (5), SOCAR (10), and Assan (12) stand out as efficient ports (DEA = 1.00) among the 17 ports included in the study. These terminals generate a level of TEU throughput that can be evaluated as efficient given their operational inputs (berth length, number of STS cranes, and number of MHCs/FCCs) (Table 3). These ports are operated, respectively, in Tekirdağ, Kocaeli, İzmir, and İskenderun, and it is assessed that there is no regional effect on port efficiency. According to the DEA results, MIP Mersin (DEA = 0.966) and Marport (DEA = 0.902) are found to be close to the efficiency frontier. For these ports to become efficient, they would need to increase their TEU throughput by 3.5% and 10.9%, respectively.

In this study, the correlation between selected capacity variables (number of STS cranes, number of MHC/FCC units, berth length) and the port efficiency scores obtained from the DEA results was examined with Pearson's r and Spearman's ρ in the jamovi statistical software (Tables 4 and 5) (R Core Team, 2024; The jamovi project, 2024). Furthermore, Cohen's (1988) threshold values ($r = 0.10$ small, $r = 0.30$ medium, $r = 0.50$ large) were taken as the basis for interpreting effect sizes. The findings indicate that there is no significant correlation between berth length and port efficiency. In addition, the number of MHC/FCC units in ports does not have a meaningful effect on port efficiency. The statistical results show that, among the capacity indicators, only the number of STS cranes has a significant relationship with port efficiency in the Pearson analysis (Table 4). Moreover, the Spearman rank correlation indicates a moderate-positive association between the STS count and port efficiency (Table 5).

Table 3. DEA efficiency results

Port	Weighted Output	Weighted Input	Difference	DEA Efficiency
1	0.965820194	1	-0.034179806	0.966
2	1	1	0	1.000
3	0.901603648	1	-0.098396352	0.902
4	0.840407628	1	-0.159592372	0.840
5	1	1	0	1.000
6	0.740506125	1	-0.259493875	0.741
7	0.610410304	1	-0.389589696	0.610
8	0.875277142	1	-0.124722858	0.875
9	0.648720485	1	-0.351279515	0.649
10	1	1	0	1.000
11	0.614117063	1	-0.385882937	0.614
12	1	1	0	1.000
13	0.533007747	1	-0.466992253	0.533
14	0.762377853	1	-0.237622147	0.762
15	0.193060671	1	-0.806939329	0.193
16	0.413786452	1	-0.586213548	0.414
17	0.071403208	1	-0.928596792	0.071

Table 4. Correlation between input variables and port efficiency (Pearson r)

Variable	Port Efficiency	
	Pearson r	p (two-tailed)
Berth Length (m)	0.306	0.233
Number of STS Cranes	0.547	0.023
Number of MHC/FCC Units	-0.270	0.294

Table 5. Correlation between input variables and port efficiency (Spearman's rho)

Variable	Port Efficiency	
	Spearman's rho	p (two-tailed)
Berth Length (m)	0.069	0.792
Number of STS Cranes	0.483	0.049
Number of MHC/FCC Units	-0.197	0.448

5. Discussion and Conclusion

Port efficiency has been addressed in numerous studies as one of the key dimensions of port performance (e.g., Cullinane & Wang, 2010; Jiang et al., 2012). Furthermore, in DEA studies, researchers may evaluate different numbers and categories of input and output variables. Nevertheless, it is important that DEA-based port efficiency analyses be regularly repeated—even if using different input and output sets—and that the results be shared with both academic and industry stakeholders. In this regard, the present study contributes to extant literature through an analysis that uses recent data. The study employs the classical CCR method under an output-oriented (TEU throughput) and constant returns to scale assumption. A total of 17 ports operating in Türkiye that provide container handling services are selected as decision-making units (DMUs). According to the analysis, in which annual TEU throughput is assessed as the output and berth length (m) and berth equipment counts (STS, MHC/FCC) are assessed as the inputs, the ports of Asyaport, DP World Yarımca, SOCAR, and Assan stand out as efficient ports.

One interesting finding of the study is that the geographical region in which a port is located does not have a significant effect on port efficiency. Among the 17 ports included in the analysis, the four efficient ports are located in Tekirdağ, Kocaeli, İzmir, and İskenderun. Another finding of the research is that berth length and the number of MHC/FCC units do not have a significant effect on port efficiency. By contrast, a positive and statistically significant relationship was identified between the number of STS cranes and output-based port efficiency.

The modification of the input and output variables used in the analysis, and the inclusion of different variables as inputs and outputs in the model, may change the research findings. In this regard, one of the limitations of this study is that the variables used in the analysis were determined based on the availability of data. It is recommended that future studies be repeated using recent data and by evaluating different variables as inputs and outputs.

In the analysis, ports engaged in container handling services were taken into consideration, and it should be noted that this may lead to ports for which container handling is a secondary activity being identified as inefficient. In addition, in multi-purpose ports and terminals, berth length is generally not reported specifically by cargo category. This situation may result in some ports being identified as having low efficiency. The findings of the research should be interpreted and analyzed in light of these limitations.

One further limitation of this study concerns the exclusion of water depth from the model. As noted in the methodology section, the model configuration and data structure led to the water-depth-related input being omitted. Moreover, TÜRKLİM (2024) data show that the majority of the ports (13 out of 17) are clustered roughly within the 14.5–18.5 m depth range, with only a few ports being significantly shallower (9.5 and 13 m) or deeper (21.5 and 28 m). For this reason, water depth was not regarded as a discriminating factor in the context of this model. Nevertheless, since water depth remains a critical factor for port competitiveness, it is recommended that it be included in future studies where the model configuration allows. Similarly, the model can be extended by incorporating “yard area” metric as an additional model element in future studies. Additionally, digital technologies such as the terminal operating systems (e.g., Eyit et al., 2022) may also be suitable for use as model inputs.

Finally, due to data-related issues, some ports (Yılport Gebze, Yılport Gemlik, Gempport, and Samsunport) are excluded from the DMU set. Therefore, the findings are specific to sample data of 17 ports, and should not be generalized to all ports operating in Türkiye, as this could introduce bias.

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